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ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION FORECAST AND GROUPING FOR FORECASTING

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Annotation: This article emphasizes the importance of forecasting electricity consumption by the population and forecasting power systems, as well as the forecasting period. In addition, information is provided on the timing of forecasting in electricity, potential outcomes, type of information source, level of reliability, overall direction, grouping of indicators, dynamic level and other groupings.

Key words: Electric power systems, forecasting, forecasting, grouping.

Forecasting is an integral part of any area of human activity. Including the energy sector is no exception. An important indicator of the standard of living of a society is the relative consumption of electricity by the population and industrial enterprises or organizations represents the level of improvement of the infrastructure of cities and other settlements. In all developed countries, this indicator is growing steadily.

To increase the efficiency and sustainability of the automated power management process, the management system should include a time series forecasting subsystem, in particular, power consumption forecasting. Electricity consumption forecasts form the main source data for planning optimal operating modes and making decisions in the process of power system development. However, the highest requirements are for short-term forecasting (day-week-month) and operational (current day) within applies to the accuracy of forecasts as they determine the control of the current regime of power systems. However, the highest requirements apply to the accuracy of short-term (day-week-month) and operational (within the current day) forecasts because they are electric determines the control of the current mode of power systems. The main tasks to be solved on the basis of electricity consumption forecasts can be divided into:

- 1) planning of development of capacities and electric networks generated by electric power systems;
- 2) planning of electricity tariffs;
- 3) planning of power load, power and power generation and fuel needs of power plants for the next day;
- 4) planning the repair of basic equipment of power plants and networks.

The demand for high accuracy of electricity consumption forecast will counteract the complex and unconventional behavior of the time sequence that characterizes consumption. Many factors affecting both regular and random consumption levels, continuous changes in energy market demand, as well as the development of power systems further complicates the task of increasing the accuracy of electricity consumption forecasting. Thus, this task needs to be addressed in the context of uncertainty.

Forecasting in electricity can be divided into the following groups

By time:

- 1) during the day on the basis of current (daily) electricity consumption;
- 2) short-term - less than a year (often, taking into account changes in temperature, periods are used that describe seasonal changes in winter electricity consumption);
- 3) medium-term - from 1 to 3 years;

4) long-term - 3 years or more (for future hypothetical situation, given the uncertainty based on possible options for the development of the power complex itself and its associated factors).

According to the potential outcome of the forecast:

1) moderate;

2) low-optimal forecasts. Factors influencing the forecast are favorable environment (relatively average air temperature, low fuel prices, etc.);

3) taking into account the growing impact of negative factors;

By level:

1) macro-forecasting - forecasting at the level of the whole power system of the country; 2) mesoprognosis - forecasting at the level of individual types of regional economic activity;

3) micro-forecasting - forecasting at the level of a group of enterprises, individual enterprises, their individual divisions.

According to the source of forecasts in the field of power engineering:

1) accumulated experience on the basis of knowledge of the laws of predictable processes (expert assessment);

2) statistical data are based on the extrapolation of existing trends;

3) creation of models of forecasted objects.

in terms of reliability.

1) high level of reliability;

2) moderate reliability;

3) low level of reliability.

Objectives:

1) target forecasting includes forecasting based on the developed efficiency (for example, reliability of electricity supply);

2) search forecasting - the development of a number of management decisions and future decisions. It is important to assess the future, taking into account the specific characteristics of the activity;

3) creative forecasting to provide assumptions about the interdependence of different elements, the processes of the projected object.

Prediction of play:

1) retrospective forecast - allows you to forecast data from the previous period and compare the obtained values with the variables (real) data.

2) future forecast - is forecasted on the basis of real data.

By grouping indicators:

1) forecast of one or more independent indicators;

2) forecast of several interrelated indicators (for example, several items of the electrical balance in the complex).

By level of dynamics:

1) static-time forecasts;

2) dynamic-accounting allows to obtain various possible parameters of the system (presence / absence of input / output power, weather conditions), as well as the relationship between its individual elements (its forecast calculation of electricity import / export balance);

according to the degree of exposure to the forecasting environment:

1) active forecasting, which has the ability to manage the factors affecting the forecast state of the object;

2) forecasting without the ability to control and manage the processes affecting the passive object;

the most convenient option for active-passive-electric power, including dependent factors (e.g., new power input) and uncontrollable (e.g., power plant accidents, abnormally high / low air temperatures).

In terms of accuracy:

1) deterministic predictions are characterized by high accuracy, the basis of which often consists of identified functional dependencies;

2) stochastic forecasts are based on the evaluation of statistical data and have a probabilistic character;

3) instability of forecasting processes in uncertainty, uncontrollable factors, limited amount of information.

Other forecasting classifications are also used, but the ones mentioned above are the most commonly used in relation to the power complex because they are the most accurate.

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